

SPORTS INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE PROTECTION MANAGEMENT MODEL IN HUNAN PROVINCE, CHINA

QIUXIA TANG

Doctoral Student, Sport Management, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand. Email: s63484950011@ssru.ac.th

Dr. BUNJOB PIROMKAM

Associate Professor, Lecturer, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand. Email: bunjob.pi@ssru.ac.th

Dr. NUTTAVUT PHONSRI

Lecturer, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand.
Email: nuttavut.ph@ssru.ac.th

PASSAPONG PIROMKAM

Lecturer, Faculty of Education and Development sciences, Kasetsart University, Kamphaeng Saen Campus, Thailand. Email: passapong.piro@ku.ac.th

Abstract

With the rapid development of the Chinese economy and the acceleration of urbanization, we have intentionally or unintentionally destroyed and buried many valuable intangible cultural heritage around us. The lack of management models by the government in protecting and managing intangible cultural heritage sites is an important reason for the loss of intangible cultural heritage. Therefore, I am conducting research on this topic. The objective of this research were to: 1) To study the current situation and affecting factors of sports intangible cultural heritage protection management in Hunan province, China.2) To analyze factors positive effect sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China.3) To Examine and evaluate sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining a quantitative and qualitative research methods. Step1: In the qualitative research section, select 10 experts for interviews, analyze and understand the current situation and influencing factors of the sports intangible cultural heritage protection management in Hunan province, China. Step2: In the quantitative research section, the sample consists of 480 respondents and is obtained through sampling. The sample size is calculated using a method used to determine that the sample size is 20 times the inventory variable. Collect data using questionnaire survey method and analyze using structural equation modeling (SEM). Step3: Select 10 experts, Analyze the information in focus group discussions through content analysis and quantitative research. Evaluate the feasibility, suitability, practicality, and accuracy of experts in intangible cultural heritage. The research results show that: There are several key aspects of the current development status of sports intangible cultural heritage protection management in Hunan province: 1)1. Development history of protection management.2. Current status of management mode.3. Protection management dilemma.4. Improvement suggestions. For the protection and management of intangible cultural heritage, it is necessary to address multiple issues and adopt comprehensive policies and measures in order to effectively address existing challenges and problems.2) There are six factors: Government functional, Ecological environmental, Cultural resource, Socio economic, Inheritor, Inheritance subject, that have a significant positive impact on the sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China. Among then, 3) Experts evaluate the feasibility, appropriateness, usefulness, and accuracy of the sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China high level and their opinions remain consistent.

Therefore, this study helps to understand the overall status and influencing factors, sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China, and to construct a development model, promote and apply it, laying a theoretical foundation for research related to the protection and management of intangible cultural relics in sports in China.

Keywords: Sports Intangible, Cultural Heritage, Protection Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research background

With the rapid development of the Chinese economy and the acceleration of urbanization, we have intentionally or unintentionally destroyed and buried many valuable intangible cultural heritage around us.

Protecting, inheriting, and making good use of intangible cultural heritage is of great significance for continuing historical context, strengthening cultural confidence, promoting cultural exchange and mutual learning, and building a socialist cultural power.

The purpose of this study is to create a management model for local intangible cultural heritage of sports, so that Hunan's intangible cultural heritage of sports can continue to develop, inherit and develop traditional culture, and promote local economic development.

That is why researchers are interested in studying the management model of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan. The research results will be used to support research and promote the sustainable development of the intangible cultural heritage industry in Hunan Province.

1.2 Research objectives

To study the current situation and affecting factors of sports intangible cultural heritage protection management in Hunan province, China. To analyze factors positive effect sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China.

To Examine and evaluate sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China.

1.3 Research steps

- (1) Using qualitative research and structured interview methods, the current situation and influencing factors of the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province were investigated.
- (2) Using quantitative research methods to develop the protection and management model of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province, China.
- (3) A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods was used to investigate and evaluate the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Research on government functions

The functions of the government vary depending on the country's political system, social system, cultural traditions, economic development status, and historical legacy issues (Wang, 2019). Government functions refer to the various responsibilities and obligations that the government fulfills, with the aim of ensuring the normal operation of the country and society (Gao, 2020).

2.2 Research on ecological environment

Ecological environment refers to the environment where people, culture, natural environment, and social environment are integrated, supporting and promoting cultural inheritance and development (Yi, 2022). Cultural heritage sites, cultural festivals and activity venues, residences and heritage communities of inheritors, natural factors affecting intangible cultural heritage, relevant social systems and values (Huang, 2021).

2.3 Research on cultural resources

Various resources with certain value and significance in the cultural field are the accumulation and embodiment of human society and historical culture (Liu, 2013). Cultural resources can include material heritage with cultural significance and historical value, such as natural landscapes, historical buildings, and relics (Li, 2020).

2.4 Research on socio economic

Socio economy refers to the impact of human behavior and decision-making on social and economic activities, as well as on society and its structure. Socio economy refers to the interweaving and interaction of economic, social, cultural, environmental, political, and other aspects. It not only involves the economy of currency, production, and circulation, but also concerns about social welfare, equity, social policies, and social structure (Chang, 2023).

2.5 Research on inheritors

The inheritor of intangible cultural heritage in sports refers to an individual who has rich experience and professional knowledge in the field of traditional sports, or has skills recognized by the state as intangible cultural heritage in sports. They are committed to inheriting, promoting, and developing specific traditional sports projects (Mai, 2023).

2.6 Research on inheritance subject

Specific intangible cultural heritage protection projects include specific skill inheritance, cultural festivals, traditional performances, etc. These projects are usually initiated and promoted by relevant organizations, institutions, or individuals, aiming to protect, inherit, and promote the development of intangible cultural heritage (Wang, 2023).

2.7 Conceptual framework

Figure 1: Framework diagram

2.8 Research hypothesis

- H1: Governmental functions affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.
- H2: Ecological environment affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.
- H3: Cultural resource affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.
- H4: Social economy affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.
- H5: Inheritor affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.
- H6: Inheritance subject affect management model on sports intangible cultural heritage protection in Hunan Province.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Step 1 research tool: The tool used in this study is structured interviews. Expert interviews are scheduled in advance. This structured interview is essentially very standard or formal. All respondents will answer the same question. The questions will be presented in order, and the interviewer must first read the questions in the interview form.

Step 2 research tool: The tool used in this study is a questionnaire aimed at investigating the factors influencing the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province. It is divided into three parts: (1) a questionnaire about the overall situation of the respondents, which includes closed questions such as education level, position, and experience. (2) Investigation on the influencing factors of the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province. By analyzing relevant literature and conducting interviews.

These questions are classified based on the components/indicators of open-ended questions. This is the 5-level quality type of the Likert scale, and the researchers divided the scores into 5 levels. (3) Open ended questioning to collect respondents' opinions or suggestions on the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province.

Step 3 research tool: Discuss opinions and information with experts through focus group discussions. Using the evaluation table for the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province, analyze the information in the focus group discussion through qualitative and quantitative research. Evaluate the feasibility, appropriateness, usefulness, and accuracy of experts in intangible cultural heritage.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Research status and influencing factors

4.1.1 Research status

(1) Current status of the development process of protection management

It was found that among the series of measures taken by the Hunan Provincial Government, policy documents have a single performance and are mainly focused on project lists. This indicates that intangible cultural heritage is facing some serious challenges and problems. Firstly, this may mean that the government does not attach enough importance to this aspect and policy support is not in place.

A single policy may not fully cover all aspects of intangible cultural heritage protection, such as inheritance, financial support, and legal regulations, without targeted policies tailored to different situations. Therefore, this analysis indicates that the government does not attach enough importance to cultural protection, and also indicates that the differences and special needs in the protection of different intangible cultural heritage have not been given sufficient attention.

(2) Current status of management mode

In recent years, Hunan has made many efforts in inheriting the intangible cultural heritage of sports, including continuously optimizing the team of inheritors of intangible cultural heritage, supplementing representative projects of intangible cultural heritage, organizing national and regional intangible cultural heritage publicity and exhibition activities, and cultivating local intangible cultural heritage activity brands in Hunan. These efforts are still being steadily implemented and promoted. Through standardized management and effective protection measures, the inheritance of intangible cultural heritage in sports can be guaranteed, its dissemination and development in contemporary society can be promoted, the public's interest in traditional sports culture can be stimulated, and its active development can be promoted.

(3) Protection management dilemma

Firstly, the outflow of rural population and the widening interpersonal distance may lead to the weakening of inheritance methods and insufficient content inheritance. Due to the fact that young people choose to work and live in cities, traditional ways of inheriting intangible cultural heritage may be affected, leading to partial action losses and insufficient digital inheritance.

Secondly, improper preservation and inheritance methods can lead to the loss and damage of intangible cultural heritage, which is also related to the imperfect legal construction. There may be loopholes and imperfections in laws and regulations, which cannot effectively protect intangible cultural heritage.

Thirdly, overall insufficient funds, unreasonable distribution, and scattered and limited fiscal investment are also issues. This leads to a lack of necessary financial support and resource integration for the protection of intangible cultural heritage.

Fourthly, the public's awareness of the protection and importance of intangible cultural heritage is insufficient, and there is a lack of active attention and support for intangible cultural heritage.

Fifthly, the lack of innovative protection methods also limits the protection of intangible cultural heritage. The relatively single means of protection management and insufficient promotion are also challenges. Multiple means and technologies are needed to protect intangible cultural heritage, including digital technology, educational promotion, etc.

Sixth, the protection of intangible cultural heritage is facing a situation of weakened inheritance methods and insufficient content inheritance. This may mean that the inheritance of traditional skills, customs, and knowledge is at risk of being cut off and lost. The decline of inheritance methods may be related to the modernization process and the weakening interest of the younger generation in traditional culture.

Therefore, it is necessary to consider how to stimulate young people's interest in intangible cultural heritage, encourage their participation in inheritance and protection work, to ensure that these valuable cultural heritage can be inherited.

4.1.2 Influencing factors

The development of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province needs to be based on a high standard political system, sound laws and regulations, and continuous industrial promotion.

This not only includes excavating international level intangible cultural heritage projects, protecting precious materials, rules, cultural relics, equipment and equipment of intangible cultural heritage, but also involves enhancing the organization and management capabilities of competitive events at the international and national levels, as well as enhancing their social influence through media and social platforms.

The specific influencing factors include: Government functional factors, such as establishing mechanisms, legislative protection, tax reduction and exemption, widespread dissemination, identification and management, etc.

The ecological environment factors include the influence of geographical location, the relationship between living and residential environments, and population mobility, which also have an important impact on the protection and management of intangible cultural heritage of sports in Hunan Province; Cultural resources play an important role in the dissemination and promotion of intangible cultural heritage in sports, specifically in traditional festivals, historical culture, and festival ceremonies; Socio economic factors include economic support, school education, and media promotion.

The inheritor is a key figure in the inheritance of sports intangible cultural heritage, They inherit traditional sports knowledge, skills, norms, etc. through oral teaching, demonstration and deduction, and protect these cultural heritage from being forgotten; The inheritor is an important component of a specific community's cultural structure, with the function of carrying and transmitting specific cultural values, knowledge, and skills. It includes traditional performing arts, handicrafts, oral traditions, etc.

4.2 Structural equation model

After the formal confirmation of the research questionnaire, we immediately entered the data collection stage. The data collection process of this study was based on simple random sampling, and 500 survey questionnaires were distributed through an online questionnaire platform.

After the questionnaire was collected, in order to ensure data quality and analysis accuracy, this study strictly screened and eliminated invalid samples, and ultimately retained 480 valid questionnaires, with an effective rate of 96%, providing a reliable and solid foundation for subsequent data analysis and research.

Table1: Variable dimensions and abbreviations

Variable	Dimensions	Abbreviations	Variable	Dimensions	Abbreviations
Governmental functions GF	Policy system	PS	Socio economic SE	Educational factors	EF
	Laws and regulations	LR		Media promotion	MP
	Personnel training	PT		Economic support	ES
Ecological environment EE	Traffic conditions	TCO	Cultural resources CR	Traditional customs	TCU
	Resident modality	RM		Festival activities	FA
	Population distribution	PD		Historical development	HD
Inheritor IH	Age and physical condition	AP	Inheritance subject ISU	Project Rules	PR
	Sense of responsibility	SR		Technical actions	TA
	Inheriting skills	ISK		Equipment props	EP
	Subsequent cultivation	SC			
Sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China IFC				public satisfaction	PSA
				Project increase	SI
				Increase in Awards	TN

4.2.1 Variable description and reliability analysis

According to the evaluation criteria of Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient, when the Cronbach's Alpha value reaches or exceeds 0.7, it can be considered as high reliability; When the value is between 0.35 and 0.70, it indicates that the reliability is still acceptable; When the Cronbach's Alpha value is below 0.35, it is considered low reliability. The statistical results are shown in the table below.

Table 2: Dimension mean and reliability coefficient

Variable	Dimensions	Average value	Cronbach's Alpha	Variable	Dimensions	Average value	Cronbach's Alpha
GF	PS	4.305	0.911	EE	TCO	4.320	0.895
	LR	4.255	0.902		RM	4.250	0.890
	PT	4.245	0.912		PD	4.265	0.898
SE	EF	4.345	0.921	IH	AP	4.428	0.940
	MP	4.365	0.930		SR	4.370	0.951
	ES	4.320	0.936		ISK	4.345	0.932
CR	TCU	4.358	0.893	ISU	SC	4.390	0.935
	FA	4.395	0.932		PR	4.333	0.946
	HD	4.300	0.945		TA	4.318	0.917
IFC	PSA	4.164	0.918	IFC	EP	4.303	0.947
	TN	4.196	0.929		SI	4.130	0.916

This study used Cronbach's Alpha coefficient as a measurement tool to evaluate the reliability of research concepts and their various dimensions in the sample. The analysis results are shown in Table 2, and the Cronbach's Alpha values of the main constructs and their dimensions are

all above 0.8, meeting the corresponding reliability standards. Therefore, it can be concluded that the scale of this sample has high internal consistency.

4.2.2 Validity analysis

Through exploratory factor analysis of the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province. After principal component analysis and applying the maximum variance method to rotate the factor matrix, the factor loadings of each indicator exceeded 0.4, indicating a strong correlation between each factor and its corresponding item. Meanwhile, the KMO value is 0.962, which is greater than 0.7, further verifying the applicability of the data. Based on the cumulative variance explanation rate of 66.385%, it can be concluded that from the perspective of exploratory factor analysis, the validity of the Hunan Province Sports Intangible Cultural Heritage Protection and Management Model Scale is good.

4.2.3 AVE and CR

From the perspective of exploratory factor analysis, the validity of the Factor Scale is better. Further confirmatory factor analysis is used to explore the structural validity of the Factor Scale.

Table 3: Dimension mean and reliability coefficient

Variable	AVE	CR	Variable	AVE	CR	Variable	AVE	CR
AP	0.849	0.957	ISU	0.786	0.978	HD	0.858	0.960
CR	0.786	0.963	LR	0.772	0.931	IFC	0.765	0.967
EE	0.749	0.957	MP	0.828	0.951	IH	0.714	0.976
EF	0.809	0.944	PD	0.766	0.929	IIF	0.765	0.982
EIF	0.779	0.985	PR	0.861	0.961	ISK	0.829	0.951
EP	0.863	0.962	PS	0.790	0.938	TCU	0.759	0.926
ES	0.840	0.954	PSA	0.754	0.939	TN	0.780	0.947
FA	0.831	0.952	PT	0.792	0.938	SC	0.838	0.954
GF	0.779	0.962	RM	0.753	0.924	SE	0.754	0.973
SI	0.749	0.937	SR	0.872	0.964	TA	0.801	0.942
						TCO	0.761	0.927

The relevant parameters for analyzing the convergence effectiveness of influencing factors are shown in the table above. As shown in the table, AVE values are all greater than 0.70, indicating that latent variables have good convergence effectiveness; The CR values are all greater than 0.90, indicating that the latent variables have good combined reliability; The confirmatory factor analysis of this structural model indicates that it fits well with the data, has good explanatory and predictive power, and has a good fitting effect. Therefore, from the perspective of confirmatory factor analysis, the validity of the influencing factor scale is relatively good.

4.2.4 Correlation analysis

This study conducted a correlation analysis on key variables in policy systems, laws and regulations, and talent cultivation, and summarized some of the results in the table below. Given the large amount of data, the table below only shows some representative results.

Table 4: Correlation analysis between variables

Variable	PS1	PS2	PS3	PS4	LR1	LR2	TN5
PS1	1							
PS2	0.604	1						
PS3	0.644	0.696	1					
PS4	0.569	0.606	0.607	1				
LR1	0.585	0.544	0.581	0.533	1			
LR2	0.526	0.561	0.552	0.576	0.629	1		
.....	
TN5	0.251	0.271	0.306	0.263	0.277	0.296	1

From the results presented in the table, it can be seen that the Spearman correlation coefficients between most variables are greater than 0, which significantly indicates a positive correlation between variables such as policy systems, laws and regulations, and talent cultivation. Based on this observation, it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between the variables, which conforms to the expected hypothesis. This provides strong basis and support for further structural equation analysis in this study.

4.2.5 Determine measurement model

Within the framework of structural equation modeling, the measurement model provides a detailed description of the specific relationship between latent variables and their respective observed variables, which is commonly referred to as the measurement model. Given that this study uses questionnaire surveys as the main data collection method, it is necessary to carefully design question options closely related to latent variables, which are the specific manifestations of observed variables. The path model in this study is shown in Figure 2, which intuitively displays the action paths and correlation relationships between various variables.

Figure 2: Path model diagram for this study

4.2.6 Significance assessment

By comparing the t-values, this study can accurately evaluate the significance level of causal relationships between variables. In this study, the significance test results of the path coefficients of the structural equation model are shown in Table 4.

Table 5: The significance test results of the path coefficients of the structural equation model in this study

	O	M	STDEV	O/STDEV	Significant level	P values
EIF -> IFC	0.618	0.613	0.060	10.302	***	0.000
IIF -> IFC	0.269	0.270	0.060	3.825	***	0.000

Note: NS=not significant, meaning not significant

*P<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

From table 5, it can be seen that:

Due to the t values being higher than 3.29 and the P value being 0.000, all influencing factors have a significant impact on the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province.

4.3 Inspection and evaluation

4.3.1 Quantitative research on model evaluation

Using the evaluation table for the protection and management mode of excellent sports intangible cultural heritage in Hunan Province, analyze the information in the focus group discussion through content analysis and quantitative research. Evaluate the feasibility, suitability, practicality, and accuracy of experts in intangible cultural heritage. Due to the large amount of data, the following is only a partial presentation.

Table 6: Mean and standard deviation of model evaluation

Factors influencing the Sports intangible cultural heritage protection management model in Hunan province, China	Opinions on the actual implementation of the model								Opinion level
	Feasibility		Useful		Appropriate		Accuracy		
	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
GF	\bar{x} 3.800 –4.600		SD 0.516–0.675						support
EE	\bar{x} 3.900 –4.500		SD 0.422–0.823						support
CR	\bar{x} 4.000 –4.600		SD 0.422–0.789						support
SE	\bar{x} 3.900 –4.600		SD 0.316–0.632						support
IH	\bar{x} 4.100 –4.500		SD 0.316–0.876						support
ISU	\bar{x} 3.800 –4.600		SD 0.422–0.738						support
IFC	\bar{x} 3.900 –4.700		SD 0.316–0.789						support
Total	\bar{x} 3.800 –4.700		SD 0.316–0.876						

Describe the overall situation of the data through mean and standard deviation. From the table below, it can be seen that the average score of the feasibility, appropriateness, usefulness, and accuracy of the research model is higher than 3.8, indicating high implementation conditions.

4.3.2 Group evaluation

Through the research group, the protection and management model of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province has been approved. This study convened a group of 10 industry stakeholders to summarize and validate previous research. Firstly, the researchers reported on their previous research findings and individually asked the group members. Secondly, group members confirm the survey results and provide comments according to the key groups. Finally, the researchers collected the opinions of experts on the results of the conference discussions.

Government functions in the protection and management of intangible cultural heritage in sports. We need to formulate relevant policies and regulations, organize investigations and protection of intangible cultural heritage, promote the inheritance and development of traditional sports projects and skills, establish relevant systems and mechanisms, strengthen supervision and guidance of related activities, and promote the protection and inheritance of intangible cultural heritage. The role of ecological environment in the protection and management of sports intangible cultural heritage provides an important natural environment foundation for the inheritance of sports intangible cultural heritage, and also provides a good natural resource guarantee for people to carry out traditional sports activities. The role of cultural resources in the protection and management of sports intangible cultural heritage is irreplaceable. It is the foundation for the inheritance of sports intangible cultural heritage. Therefore, the government and society should strengthen the protection and excavation of cultural resources to promote the inheritance and development of sports intangible cultural heritage. The social economy complements each other in the protection and management of intangible cultural heritage in sports, providing necessary conditions and guarantees for the protection and inheritance of intangible cultural heritage. The government and society should strengthen their support and investment in the social, economic, and educational fields to promote the protection of intangible cultural heritage in sports. The inheritors have made important contributions to the inheritance and protection of intangible cultural heritage in sports through their own efforts and practices. The government and society should strengthen training and support for inheritors to ensure effective protection and inheritance of sports intangible cultural heritage.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

In the development process of the protection and management model of sports intangible cultural heritage in Hunan Province, six factors, including government functions, ecological environment, inheritor, social economy, and inheritance subject, have a significant positive impact on the development of the protection and management model of sports intangible

cultural heritage in Hunan Province. The research results indicate that the factors affecting the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province are closely related to its six components. Therefore, this study helps to use structural equation modeling to measure the factors that affect the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage of sports in Hunan Province in various ways.

5.2 Discussion

This study constructed a structural equation model for sports intangible cultural heritage protection management in Hunan Province, China, and found that government functional, ecological environmental, cultural resource, social economic, inheritor, and inheritance subjects have a significant positive impact on it. Based on this, the study proposes corresponding suggestions, including Building a government functional system, strengthening ecological environment protection, enhancing the value of cultural resources, promoting social and economic development, innovating inheritance mechanisms for inheritors, and protecting and inheriting major resources.

5.3 Suggestion

Building a government functional system, strengthening ecological environment protection, enhancing the value of cultural resources, promoting social and economic development, innovating inheritance mechanisms for inheritors, and protecting and inheriting major resources. This study aims to explore in depth the influencing factors of the protection and management mode of intangible cultural heritage in sports in Hunan Province. Subsequent researchers will also attempt to conduct relevant research on the influencing factors of the protection and management models of intangible cultural heritage in other countries and regions, and compare and analyze the results of this study to expand the external effectiveness of the research.

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